

Upcycled Waste Plastic as 2025 Home Accessories

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Abstract

Fablab Bohol as the first FABLAB in the Philippines together with the JICA Volunteers and local makers develop this machine called "Heat Press Machine". This press machine allows to maximize the use of waste shopping bags thru converting it into an Upcycled Plastic Sheets as a new raw material. The main thrust of this study was to design, fabricate and assess the functionality of Upcycled Plastic Sheets as a Material for a Home Accessories Collection. This experiment further sought to verify the result of the physical and performance level of the material and the acceptability of the material applied in Home Accessories Collection.

As the result of the development of 2025 Home Accessories Collection from upcycled plastic sheets is acceptable as a new alternative material for Home Accessories, according to the respondents for the acceptability level from Cebu City Philippines where also been recognized by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) Network of Creative Cities as a "City of Design". Thus, the use of upcycled plastic sheets could be applied into various designs of Home Accessories. It implies that the development of this project thru Fablab has a significant impact to the community.

Keywords

Digital Fabrication, Plastic Upcycling, Industrial Design, Material Manipulation, Home Accessories

1 Introduction

One of the exciting aspects of Design is the ability to try new materials and ideas in order to change the way one perceives a new product. Either by combining materials or improving its common state, designers find the true beauty of a product directly from the materials being used.

In Bohol Philippines, the Bohol Island State University (BISU) opened Fablab Bohol Philippines (FABLAB) with its cooperating Agencies – Japan International Cooperating Agency (JICA), Department of Trade and Industry - Bohol Province (DTI) and City of Tagbilaran was able to create a machine capable of transforming waste plastic bags into plastic sheets that is made of waste plastic specifically the mixed Low-Density polyethylene and the High-Density polyethylene, This process is called Upcycling, otherwise called innovative reuse, it is the way toward changing by-products, waste materials, useless, or undesirable items into new materials or products of better quality or for better environmental value or a creation or modification of a product from used materials, components and products which are of equal or higher quality or value than the original. The researcher observed that plastic sheets upcycling is already applied in different fashion accessories and wearables by different local firms. Hence, the researcher being an Industrial Designer is also motivated to test the material's durability by applying into different Home Accessories Products, to validate its flexural strength, tensile strength, water and heat resistance. Home accessories as portable accessories represent the style of the owner and create a unique atmosphere where they are placed. With these ideas and realities, the researcher was motivated to design, make, and assess the functionality of the upcycled plastic sheets as a material for Home Accessories.

2 Background

Stepping up plastic waste prevention, preparation for re-use, recycling and separate plastic waste collection, as well as improving plastic design and plastic product design are all essential contributors to help achieve 'zero plastic to landfill' and move to a circular economy. Plastic products and plastic waste are two sides of the same coin and recycling already starts in the product design phase. Designers need to be involved in the reflection on the entire life cycle of products including the waste phase. All factors in designing, producing, using and disposing of plastic products and handling plastic waste will have to contribute to a less wasteful economy (Potočnik et.al. 2013).

At present, Tagbilaran City goes for ZERO-WASTE, strictly implementing RA 9003 Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000 of the Republic of the Philippines stating as follows: (a) Ensure the protection of public health and environment; (b) Utilize environmentally-sound methods that maximize the utilization of valuable resources and encourage resources conservation and recovery; (c) Set guidelines and targets for solid waste avoidance and volume reduction through source reduction and waste minimization measures, including composing, recycling, re-use, recovery, green charcoal process, and others. Some of the purpose of this Act: Recovered material shall refer to material and by-products that have been recovered or diverted from solid waste for the purpose of being collected, processed and used as a raw material in the manufacture of a recycled product. RA 9003 mandates that there should be a segregation at source and a "No Segregation, No Collection" policy. Further, it states that barangays will have a materials recovery facility (MRF), where waste materials are sorted for composting and recycling, and the residual waste will be brought to the sanitary landfills.

In Tagbilaran City Bohol being an industrialized city, based on records of the Bohol Environmental Management Office (BEMO) year 2017, it was estimated that 9,452 kilograms of wastes are generated daily from Tagbilaran City that accumulated a massive non-biodegradable waste. Lito Taladua of Solid Waste Management Office (SWMO) said that BIODEGRADABLES (food and kitchen wastes, fruit and vegetable residuals) are not collected by the SWMO. Households should have a compost pit in their backyard. Recyclable wastes like newspaper, tin cans, and bottles should be brought to the junk shops.

According to Porcalla, of the Philippine Star (2018) the Philippines has become the world's third largest source of plastic leaking into the ocean and has among the highest trash collection rates in Southeast Asia. This is igniting an alarming state. The academe has a lead role to play in order to respond to these challenging realities.

In 2019, the City government of Tagbilaran Bohol Philippines and the Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA) teamed up for a project "Plastic Sheets Upcycling" that sought to sustain economic interests while protecting the environment by upcycling plastic shopping bags into fashion accessories and wearables products made by Kalipunan ng Liping Pilipina (KALIPi) Women, a women's association in the said city, It was with the help the PRP4IWI or the Plastic Recycling Project for Improving Women's Income by JICA, using Heat Press Machines customized by JICA Volunteers, Fabrication Laboratory Bohol (FABLAB BOHOL) and supported by Department of Trade and Industry Philippines – Bohol Province. Plastic Sheets Up-Cycling Project aimed to get rid of the ubiquitous plastic trash while generating an inclusive business opportunity that can generate livelihood for local communities.

The possible contribution of this study will be the introduction of the functionality of using the upcycled plastic sheets as a material for Home Accessories Products and more. This served as motivation for the researcher to create new designs and push for possible collaboration between the Industrial Design Department of Bohol Island State University and with local firms. With the findings of the study, the researcher hoped to develop more sustainable green design products.

2.1 Background. 2025 Home Accessories Collection

The name of the collections which refers to the theory about the amount of plastic in the ocean could triple by the year 2025 and continues manufacturing of it will cause climate change and affects the biodiversity.

The amount of plastic in the sea could significantly increase continuously in 2025, as indicated by another report on the future of the oceans. Considering there's as of now over 5.25 trillion pieces of plastic trash

on the world's ocean. With levels of the plastic sea pollution set to triple between 2015 and 2025, the report cautions that the current health of the seas could make them damning implications for biodiversity. Plastic litter stays perhaps the most serious issue confronting the world's oceans, alongside rising ocean levels, environmental.

The 2025 Home Accessories Collection is proposed to make use of the current waste plastics thru various method to resolve the issues of tons of waste plastics in our oceans and landfills.

Figure 1: Design Concept of the 2025 Home Accessories Collection

3 Process Assembly of the Upcycled Plastic Sheets

The 2025 Home Accessories Collection is made of upcycled waste plastic shopping bags and pressed to make a medium density polyethylene plastic sheet. The Upcycled Plastic sheets were cut and applied to the 2025 Home Accessories Collection.

- **Process 1:** Collecting waste shopping bags. To clean wash it with water and detergent powder. After washing let it dry under the sun until it dry. Once its dry then cut/shred them into pieces depends on the design pattern goal.
- **Process 2:** Use wax paper as base and cover for the shredded plastic bags before heading to the heat press machine for pressing. Wax paper will be the use to avoid undesired sticking to the machine and the plastic also from burning.
- **Process 3:** Now ready to load the cut/shredded waste plastic bag to the heat press machine to its required temperature. First will be in the heat press and next will be in the cold press in 20-30 seconds.
- **Process 4:** Now ready to unload and finish making the upcycled plastic sheets. Time duration may be depending on the thickness of the material/ upcycled plastic sheets

Figure 2: Process Assembly of the Upcycled Plastic Sheets

4 Digital Design to Digital Fabrication

The process of making the 2025 Home Accessories Collection using ULS laser cutter and Shopbot CNC Milling Machine.

Figure 4: Design Process of the 2025 Home Accessories Collection

Figure 5: Procedure on how to use Universal Laser Cutter and Shopbot CNC Milling Machine

5 Physical Properties of the Material and Performance Level of 2025 Home Accessories Collection

The test results from the Department of Science and Technology Development Institute (DOST-ITDI) in terms of tensile strength, flexural strength, and heat deflection temperature and water absorption are presented.

Table 1 shows the tensile strength of the material is 11.3 MPa which mean that with an area of one (1) inch(2) the material can carry a mass of 495.42 kg.

Sample Code	Tensile Strength (MPa)		Tensile Stress at Break (MPa)		Tensile Stress at Yield (MPa)		Elongation at Yield (%)	
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD
PPT-2019-0144	11.3	1.59	-	-	-	-	-	-
Sample Code	Elongation at Break (%)		Modulus of Elasticity (GPa)		Mean Dimension		No. of Specimen Failed	
	M	SD	M	SD	W	T	WGL	OGL
PPT-2019-0144	-	-	0.696	0.178	14.7	0.788	1	4

Test Parameters:

Test Method: ASTM
 D638 Adapted
 Speed of Test, mm/min: 5
 Gage Length, mm: 50
 No. of Replicate Test: 5
 Instrument Used:
 Shimadzu UTM, Model: AGS-50kNXD

Conditioning Atmosphere:

Temperature, °C : 23 ± 2
 Relative Humidity, % : 50 ± 5

Legend:

W – Width of Specimen
 WGL – Within Gage Length
 T – Thickness of Specimen
 OGL – Outside Gage Length
 M – Mean
 SD – Standard Deviation

Table 1: Tensile Strength

Table 2 shows the flexural strength of the material is 10.9 MPa, in a 10.8mm width and 4.34 mm thickness as dimension, that can carry a mass of 1kg.

Sample Code	Flexural Strength (MPa)		Flexural Stress at a given Strain (MPa)				Flexural Stress at Break (MPa)		Flexural Modulus (GPa)	
			3.5%		5%					
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD
PPT-2019-0144	10.9	7.76	10.2	7.43	5.85	0.765	-	-	0.498	0.383
Sample Code	Mean Dimension (mm)		No. of Specimen Failed at:			Rate of Cross Head Motion (mm/min)	Support Span Length (mm)			
	W	T	Y	R	**					
PPT-2019-0144	10.8	4.34	2	0	4	18.5	69.5			

Test Parameters:

Test Method: ASTM D790/ ISO 178 Adapted
 Type of Procedure used: B
 No. of Replicate Test: 6
 Support span-to-depth ratio: 16:1
 Radius of Support/ Loading Noses, mm: 5
 Instrument Used: Shimadzu UTM, Model: AGS-50kNXD

Conditioning Atmosphere:

Temperature, °C: 23 ± 2
 Relative Humidity, %: 50 ± 5

Legend:

W – Width of Specimen
 Y – Yield
 T – Depth/ Thickness of Specimen
 R – Rupture
 M – Mean ** did not yield nor rupture
 SD – Standard Deviation

Table 2: Flexural Strength

Table 3 shows that the material deforms at the average deflection temperature of 78.5°C. Thus, the material can be an outdoor material for home accessories since the Philippine has the maximum heat of 47°C according to Department of Science and Technology - PAG-ASA record observed last June 11, 2019.

Sample Code	Trial	Mean Dimension (mm)		Maximum Fiber Stress (Mpa)	Heat Deflection Temperature per Specimen (°C)	Average Heat Deflection Temperature (°C)
		W	T			
PPT-2019-0144	1	13.5	3.25	0.455	81.4	78.5
	2	14.6	3.80	0.455	75.5	

Test Parameters:

Test Method: ASTM D648 Method A
 No. of Replicate Test: 2
 Standard Deflection, mm: 0.25
 Initial Starting Temperature, °C: 30
 Heating Rate, °C/ min: 2 ± 0.2
 Heat Transfer Media: Silicon Oil

Instrument Used: Dynisco HDV3 Vicat/DTUL Machine

Conditioning Atmosphere:

Temperature, °C: 23 ± 2
 Relative Humidity, %: 50 ± 5

Legend: W –Width of Specimen, mm T – Thickness of Specimen, mm

Table 3: Heat Deflection Temperature

Table 4 shows that the material absorbs water and increase in 6.53% in weight if it is immersed in water for 24 hours. No change in colour, physical appearance. No disintegration was also observed.

Sample Code	% Water Absorption (Change in Weight)	Mean Dimension (mm)			Observation
		L	W	T	
PPT-2019-0144	+ 6.53	77.1	25.6	1.68	No change in color, Physical appearance. No disintegration

Test Parameters:

Test Method: ASTM D570 (adapted)
 Type of Immersion: 24h-Immersion
 No. of Replicate Test: 3
 Instrument Used: Analytical Balance

Conditioning Atmosphere:

Temperature, °C: 23 ± 2
 Relative Humidity, %: 50 ± 5

Table 4: Water Absorption

Table 6 Presents the Acceptability Level of Upcycled Plastic Sheets as Materials for 2025 Home Accessories Collection. It reflects that respondents have positive response as shown in the grand mean of 3.71 described as “highly acceptable”. This reveals that the respondents highly accepted the 2025 Home Accessories Collections using the Upcycled Plastic Sheets in terms of material used, beauty, functionality being eco-friendly and the cost.

The highest mean 3.87 which is interpreted as “very high or effective to the great extent” belongs to Material used category. This suggest that the respondents highly accepted the new material or the upcycled plastic sheets applied into the 2025 Home Accessories Collections that can extend the life span of the waste plastics and addresses the waste plastic pollution problem that our world facing. It also can be one of the way that the 2025 theory about plastic ocean pollution will be only be a theory but not reality.

However, the lowest mean 3.45 which is interpreted as “very high or effective to the great extent” belongs to the cost section which the respondents believed that the cost is expensive for a Home Accessories collections. This suggests that the cost of plastic sheets per 12 x 14 inches is too high as well as the cost of 2025 Home Accessories Collections which cost Php. 20, 250.00 (358.77 USD) which has the weighted mean of 3.31 and 3.32 and described as Highly Acceptable.

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
4	3.26 – 4.00	Highly Acceptable	The respondents believed that the level of acceptability is very high or effective to a very great extent
3	2.5 – 3.25	Acceptable	The respondents believed that the level of acceptability is high or effective to a great extent
2	1.75 – 2.49	Slightly Acceptable	The respondents believed that the level of acceptability is low or effective to a moderate extent
1	1.00 – 1.74	Not Acceptable	The respondents believed that the level of acceptability is very low or effective to the least extent

Table 5: Interpretation using the following scale

Number of Respondents -85

Items	Rating		
	Weighted Mean	Description	Rank
A. Aesthetics			
1. The pattern and color of the material has a good visual beauty or appeal.	3.73	Highly Acceptable	
2. The texture of the material is smooth and the shape is pleasing to the eye.	3.69	Highly Acceptable	
3. The collections have aesthetically pleasing designs.	3.61	Highly Acceptable	
Average Weighted Mean	3.68		4
B. Functionality			
1. There is no reaction or melting of Upcycled Plastic Sheet when applied with lightings and accessories.	3.61	Highly Acceptable	
2. The material is flexible and has the ability to bend or compress easily without cracking under normal conditions.	3.78	Highly Acceptable	
3. The material has no change in color, physical appearance and no disintegration in water.	3.74	Highly Acceptable	
Average Weighted Mean	3.71		3
C. Materials Used			
1. The materials are readily available through the effort/initiative of a group of women in the locality.	3.81	Highly Acceptable	
2. The Upcycled Plastic Sheets are made of waste plastic shopping bags.	3.96	Highly Acceptable	
3. The combination of materials gives an aesthetic and functional potential for possible products.	3.84	Highly Acceptable	
Average Weighted Mean	3.87		1
D. Cost			
1. The 2025 Home Accessories Collections is sold at Php. 20,250.00	3.32	Highly Acceptable	
2. The upcycled plastic sheets per 12x 14 inches size is Php 150.00	3.31	Highly Acceptable	
3. The cost is reasonable for the material because it lessens the problems caused by the use of plastic as well as providing sustainable livelihood to the community.	3.72	Highly Acceptable	
Average Weighted Mean	3.45		5
E. Eco-friendly			
1. Upcycled plastic shopping bags are the dominant materials for the product.	3.86	Highly Acceptable	
2. Approximately 1 kilogram of waste plastic shopping bags are being utilized for the 2025 Home Accessories Collections, hence favorably advantageous to the environment.	3.84	Highly Acceptable	
3. It extends the life span of the waste plastic shopping bags thru upcycling.	3.88	Highly Acceptable	
Average Weighted Mean	3.86		2
General Weighted Mean	3.71	Highly Acceptable	

Table 6: Acceptability of 2025 Home Accessories Collection from Upcycled Plastic Sheets

6 Findings

After a thorough analysis of the study, the researcher came up with the following findings:

1. 1. The description of 2025 Home Accessories Collections from upcycled plastic sheets were the following:
 - 1.1 The upcycled plastic sheets are available in Project Recycling Project for Improvement of Women's Income (PRP4IWI), the tools and materials needed are available locally.
 - 1.2 The design of 2025 Home Accessories Collections could be added more various design for other collections using the upcycled plastic sheets because of the flexibility of the material.
 - 1.3 The production cost of 2025 Home Accessories Collections has a good price.
 - 1.4 The machine and tools for digital fabrication is locally available.
 - 1.5 The process of assembly of the products is easy to execute.
2. It was found out that the physical properties of the upcycled plastic and performance level of 2025 Home Accessories Collections in terms of:
 - 2.1 the tensile strength of the material is 11.3 MPa which mean that with an area of one (1) inch² the material can carry a mass of 495.42 kg.;
 - 2.2 the flexural strength of the material is 10.9 MPa, in a 10.8mm width and 4.34 mm thickness as dimension, that can carry a mass of 1kg.
 - 2.3 the material deforms at the average deflection temperature of 78.5°C. Thus, the material can be an outdoor material for home accessories since the Philippine has the maximum heat of 47°C
 - 2.4 the material absorbs water and increase in 6.53% in weight if it is immersed in water for 24 hours. No change in colour, physical appearance. No disintegration was also observed.
3. For the acceptability level towards the development of 2025 Home Accessories Collections from upcycled plastic sheets, it has an average weighted mean of 3.71 which is described as highly acceptable and interpreted as effective to the great extent. The highest mean was in the materials used since the respondents believed that the material is effective that gives an aesthetic and functional potential for possible products. However, the lowest mean belongs to the cost section. This suggests that the price is too high for the respondents.
4. The output of the study could be extended to communities especially to Home Accessories, Furniture and even Fashion local firms as takers of the study to generate more income and livelihood.

7 Conclusions

Based from the findings of the study, the conclusion is formulated: The development of 2025 Home Accessories Collections from upcycled plastic sheets is acceptable as a new material for Home Accessories. Thus, the use of upcycled plastic sheets could be applied into various design of Home Accessories, Furniture, Fashion accessories and other products due to its strong physical properties.

8 Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of the study, the researcher proposes the following recommendations:

1. The researcher may consider providing the following:
 - 1.1 Design collections that promotes Filipino culture and traditions.
 - 1.2 Various Design (shapes, patterns and forms) for various target markets.

- 1.3 Combination of local material such as bamboo, rattan, nito and any other indigenous material to the upcycled plastic sheets for design framing to promote sustainable and green design.
2. The government may come up the following:
 - 2.2 Expanding the PRP4IWI pressing Facility to produce more plastic sheets and to provide more income to the locality and also can reduce more plastic waste.
 - 2.3 Upcycling programs which may include local makers, designers, exporters and firms of Bohol as takers of the study. This could be in a form of collaboration with government, non-government agencies, and private sectors.
3. The designers may use the design as an inspiration to create other product designs using upcycled plastic sheets.
4. Future researchers may replicate this study to further development of the application of the material. The procedures and contents may serve as guide in conducting related studies.
5. Application for patenting for process on how to assembly the 2025 Home Accessories collections for intellectual property protection.
6. The purpose of this study is to address the current problems with plastic waste, not to encourage the continued usage of single-use plastic.

Acknowledgement

I would like to extend my gratitude to Shiro Takaki, Yutaka Tokushima and the rest of the volunteers and makers for making this heat press machine possible and to Alfred Vicere and Fablab Bohol in-house designers for helping me on the product development stage and to my Research mentor Dr. Zina Sayson.

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